

Rainwater Harvesting: Microbial and Chemical Water Quality Assessment in Warri District

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Abstract

This study evaluated the microbial and chemical quality of harvested rainwater collected from the rooftops of different materials: zinc, aluminium, asbestos, and thatch from private dwellings and public places in Warri Refinery Petrochemical Company (WRPC), Warri, Delta State. A total of 20 rainwater samples were obtained across five rainfall events and analyzed using USEPA and APHA standard recommended methods for microbials procedures for physicochemical and microbiological parameters, including Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrate, sulphate, calcium, magnesium, total coliforms, fecal coliforms, Escherichia coli, total heterotrophic bacteria (THB), and fungi (THF). BOD results obtained ranged from 1.40–1.40 mg/L, 1.60–1.30 mg/L, 1.80–1.40 mg/L and 2.10–1.50 mg/L for aluminum, zinc, asbestos, and thatch roofing material. COD values ranged from 3.26–3.41 mg/L, 3.72–3.13 mg/L, 4.19–3.20 mg/L, and 4.88–3.66 mg/L for aluminum, zinc, asbestos, and thatch roofs samples, respectively. DO values range from 4.60–6.10 mg/L in all the roofing materials. The calcium values ranged from 1.040 – 0.395 mg/L, 2.124 – 0.659 mg/L, 2.816–1.006 mg/L, and 3.536–1.224 mg/L for zinc, aluminum, asbestos and thatch roofs, respectively, from the first fifth flush. Magnesium values ranged from 6.095–0.198 mg/L in all the roofing materials. NO_3^- values ranged from 0.02–ND mg/L, 0.03–ND mg/L, 0.19–0.01 mg/L and 0.06–ND mg/L for aluminum, zinc, asbestos, and thatch roofing materials. SO_4^{2-} values range from 0.51–6 ND mg/L in all the roofing materials. T. Coliform values ranged from 140.0 -20.00 MPN/100mL, F. Coliform from 20.00-ND MPN/100mL, THB from 2.51 – 1.07 cfu/L, THF from 1.32- 0.08 cfu/L for all the roofing materials. E.coli was not detected in all the roofing materials. All harvested rainwater samples tested positive for total coliform counts were above the World Health Organization (W.H.O) stipulation for drinkable water of 0 MPN/100ML and 0 cfu/L for THB and THF respectively. The chemicals and elemental parameters in the water samples were relatively within the World Health Organization (W.H.O) standards of 4.00, 5, 10, 50, 250, 75 and 50 mg/L for DO, BOD, COD, NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Ca and Mg. The study revealed that harvested rainwater may not be suitable for direct or indirect drinking, without proper treatment, but could be used for many other domestic purposes.

Keywords: Harvested Rainwater, Chemical, Microbiological, Rooftops

Introduction

Water is regarded as one of the most valuable natural resources widely distributed all over the world (Obruche et al., 2018). Water, after air, is the most essential commodity to the survival of life (Qingyun et al., 2008).

Human life depends to a large extent on water. It is used for an array of activities, chief among these being for drinking, food preparation, as well as for sanitation purposes. Rainwater harvesting as an alternative source of water for domestic use is becoming popular as public water supplies are not always available and consistent (Gould et al., 1999). Rainwater harvesting is a simple and low-cost technique that involves the capturing and storing of rainwater from roof catchments or directly for domestic, agricultural and environmental purposes (Adedeji and Ako, 2009). When rain falls, water is collected either directly or through catchment systems for storage and eventual use. The quality of water collected in a rainwater harvesting system is affected by many factors (Dile et al., 2013). which include: the roof materials and the nature of the catchment system, environmental pollution from automobiles industries, and anthropogenic activities, the presence of debris, dirt, rodents or birds dropping on roofs and rainwater catchments and the type of storage materials (substances) for harvested rainwater (Ogwuche and Obruch, 2020). Catchment material, treatment and storage material are three design considerations that can be put together or optimized to maximize rainwater quality. The type of roofing materials can impact or affect the quality of the rain water harvested. However, research has shown that the type of roof material will determine the quality of drinking water (Ziadat, 2005). There are reports that metal rooftops or metal-related rooftops can react with rainwater to cause rust (corrosion). For instance, high concentrations or percentages of heavy metals can easily corrode and when they have been left for a long time (during raining season). The situation has worsened by tear and wear conditions of many metal materials which release heavy metals such as zinc and aluminium, which can be toxic to humans if it exceed certain concentrations in the harvested rainwater (Al-Salaymeh et al., 2011). Adeniyi and Olabanji (2005) reported that the leaching of rooftop materials was found to be significant in a study carried out. Microorganisms found to be carried by birds and animal vectors include, *Cryptosporidium*, *Giardia*, *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* spp (Boelee et al., 2007). Each of these microorganisms is known to cause gastroenteritis and other illnesses (Hill et al., 2006).

Coliform bacteria are present or can be found in the environment and feces of all warm-blooded animals, as well as humans. Coliform bacteria are unlikely to cause severe illness. However, their presence in drinking water indicates that disease-causing organisms (pathogens) could be in the water system. Most pathogens that can contaminate water supplies come from the feces of humans or animals. There are three kinds or groups of coliform bacteria (Joanne and Gakungu, 2013). Each is an indicator of drinking water quality, is contaminated and each has a different level of risk. In addition, total coliform is a large (broad) collection of different kinds of bacteria. However, fecal coliforms are types of total coliform and they exist mostly in feces. While *E. coli* is a subgroup (small group) of fecal coliform. A wide array of pathogens could be present in the feces of birds, insects, mammals, and reptiles that have access to the roof. Consequently, following rain events, animal droppings and other organic debris deposited on the roof and gutter can be transported into the tank via roof runoff (Obruch et al., 2018). In this scenario, if the untreated water collected from the roof is used for drinking, there is a potential for disease in people consuming this water. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that for drinking water, the total coliform numbers should be <10 CFU/100 mL in 95% of samples collected from a particular water source (WHO, 2010). These guidelines also indicate that if the number of total coliforms are >20 CFU/100 mL of water, further treatment should be undertaken prior to drinking. Fecal coliforms are better indicators of fecal contamination, and most guidelines stipulate that fecal coliforms, *E. coli* numbers should be zero CFU/100 mL for drinking water (Mendez et al., 2010). Such stringent guideline values have been established for these indicators, as these are commonly found in high numbers in human and animal feces. A radical anion is a negatively charged specie, atom or molecule that have an atom bearing an unpaired or lone electron (Aladenola and Adeboye, 2009). Nitrate is an inorganic chemical that is highly soluble in water. Nitrate is a health hazard because of its conversion to nitrite (Itodo et al., 2021). Once ingested, conversion of nitrate(s) to nitrite(s) takes place in the saliva of body of all age groups, and in the gastrointestinal tract of infants (Aderogba, 2005). High concentration of nitrate above 50 mg/L in drinking water is deleterious, especially to babies due to the formation of methemoglobinemia (WHO, 2003). Nitrates occur naturally in the atmosphere, mineral deposits, in biota, seawater, freshwater systems, and in soils. Lakes and other static water bodies usually have less than 1.0 µg/L of nitrate (Greenhalgh and Faeth, 2001).

Sulphate, a major ion occurring in water, with its main source from the chemical process of dissolution of sulphur-containing minerals, such as gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Efe, 2006). Other natural sources are the oxidation of sulphides and elemental sulphur, and the decomposition of animal and plant residues can release

sulphate in water (Obruche et al., 2018). The recommended threshold concentration of sulphate in drinking water is 250 mg/L. Sulphate gives a bitter taste to drinking water if it exceeds a concentration of 250mg/L, which will make the water unpleasant to drink (Cobbina et al., 2013). Biochemical oxygen demand(BOD) is the amount of dissolved oxygen needed by aerobic organism(s) to break down organic materials present in a given water body (sample) at a certain(specified) temperature over a certain (specific) period of time (Basinger et al., 2010). A BOD of 1-2 mg/L is considered (regarded) very good. However, there will not be much organic waste present in the water at that time. Water that contains a BOD of 3-4ppm is considered moderate clean. In water bodies with a Biochemical oxygen demand(BOD) level of 6-9ppm, the water is considered or regarded somewhat polluted (contaminated) because there is usually organic matter present and bacterial are decomposing the waste (Igwo-Ezikpe and Awodele, 2010). COD measures all organic compounds that can be chemically oxidized; COD is an indirect measurement of the amount of organic matter sample. The higher the chemical oxygen demand, the higher the amount of pollution in the test samples (Obruche et al., 2019). It is measured in milligrams per liter (mg/L), which indicate the mass of oxygen consumed per liter of solution (Ahmed et al., 2008). Dissolved Oxygen is the amount of gaseous oxygen dissolved in the water. Oxygen enters water through the atmosphere, as a waste product from photosynthesis etc. Oxygen dissolves more easily in cooler water than hot or warm water (EPA, 2008). Adequate DO is important for good water quality and is also necessary for all living organisms. DO levels that are below 5.0 ml/L cause stress to aquatic organisms. Oxygen level that goes below 1-2 mg/L may result to death of large aquatic life (Akintola and Sangodoyin, 2011).

This research is to evaluate the effects or significant roles played by different roofing materials (zinc, aluminium, asbestos and thatch roof) in rainwater harvesting in Warri, in the Niger Delta Region of Southern Nigeria. For this, harvested rainwater from the four rooftops were analysed. The samples collected were checked for different microbiological and chemical water quality parameters to determine the sanitary appraisal of the harvested rainwater, and to arrive at conclusion(s).

Materials and Methods

Description of study area

Warri is the study area is Warri Refinery and Petrochemical Company (WRPC) and is located in the Warri axis of Delta state, Nigeria. The town lies within the longitudes 3°E-9°E and latitudes 4° 30'N-5° 21'N of southern oil rich Niger Delta region (Obruche et al., 2019). It has an area of 633 km² and a population of 303,417 according to the 2006 National population census of Nigeria. Delta State is situated in the Southern part of Nigeria. It has an annual rainfall of about 3000mm- 4500mm with a mean temperature of 24°C and a maximum temperature of 30°C in core dry season months like December during the day. The majority of the houses in Warri are for residential, clinical, religious (Christians), and educational purposes. The town have industries and factories. The study area was chosen because of the activities of all these many industries and factories in the area as well as human activities in the area, The major source of water for domestic uses are from boreholes and hand-dug wells, but they also augment if with rainwater during the raining season. The less privilege or poor people relies extensively on the available rainwater because it is free, accessible in the rainy season and believed to be safe for drinking.

Preliminary-Treatment of Sampling Container

To ascertain or obtain accurate results, proper sample preliminary-treatment protocol or procedures were adopted (employed) to eliminate, reduce or remove potential contamination of the harvested rainwater samples (USEPA, 2006). Sample containers were soaked in acid solution overnight prior to sample collection, followed by proper rinsing with distilled-deionized water and stored. Sample containers were adequately, clearly and properly labeled to enhance good record keeping. Rainwater samples were labeled; WRPC1, WRPC2, WRPC3, WRPC4 and WRPC5 for the first to fifth rain respectively.

Method of sampling and collection of rain water samples

The first field work was to indicate and identify the location of the roof materials in WRPC region in Warri for rainwater harvesting. Sample locations(sites) were randomly picked (selected) where rainwater harvesting system was already in existence. A random sampling method (technique) was employed (adopted) in selecting the sampled locations. Four different roofing materials namely; zinc, aluminium, thatch and asbestos were

identified. Samples of harvested rainwater from various rooftops were collected in the months of February to September, 2019. Twenty (20) samples were collected from different roofing materials (asbestos, zinc sheets, aluminium sheets and thatch roof) from the first to fifth annual rainfall of the year 2019. Care was taken to ensure (ascertain) that no mistake or accidental contaminations occur during rainwater sampling, before the samples to be analyzed (synthesize) were collected from the different rooftops. Samples for microbial analysis were kept with a sterilized capped bottle to avoid (arrest) further growth of bacterial prior to synthesis (analysis). They were then taking to the laboratory for elemental, microbial, biochemical and anions analyses.

Water Quality Analysis

All chemicals and reagents used during this research were of analytical grade and distilled water was used in the preparations and synthesis (analyses) as described by (USEPA, 2006) and (APHA, 2005).

Microbiological analysis

All the bacteriological parameters including total Heterotrophic bacteria (THB), total Coliform bacterial (TCB), fecal coliform bacteria (FCB), escherichia coli (E. coli) bacterial, and total heterotrophic Fungi (THF) test was conducted using the (USEPA, 2006) recommended multiple tube fermentation technique "MPN method" (APHA, 2005). Lauryl tryptose broth (LTB) for the Presumptive Phase (PP) of total and faecal coliforms and Brilliant green lactose bile broth (BGLBB) and EC Medium were used for the Confirmation Phases (CP) of Total coliform and Faecal coliform.

Biochemical Analysis

Bio chemicals Oxygen Demand (BOD) was carried out by Iodometric Method, Chemicals Oxygen Demand (COD) was determined using the Open Reflux Method and Dissolved oxygen (DO) was determined by winkler method. The water quality analysis (WQA) was carried out in accordance with the APHA (2005) Standard Methods and procedures for the Examination of Water and Wastewater.

Anions analysis

The determination of sulphates (SO_4^{2-}) was carried out by 'Turbidimetric method' (USEPA, 2006) and Nitrate (NO_3^-) was analyzed by UV Spectrophotometric Screening Method (APHA, 2005).

Elemental Analysis

Calcium was determined by EDTA Titrimetric Method and Magnesium analysis was carried out by Calculation Method (USEPA, 2006). Magnesium was estimated as the difference between total hardness and calcium hardness.

Magnesium (mg/L) = [Total hardness (mg CaCO_3/L) - Calcium hardness (mg CaCO_3/L)] x 0.243.

Results and Discussion

The results of the bacteriological parameters and chemical parameters of the harvested rainwater samples are shown in Tables 1-4, respectively. The results of these parameters in the harvested rainwater in different rooftops were compared with World Health Organization Standards (WHO, 2003) for drinking water.

Table 1: Chemical test result from Aluminium and zinc Roofs from first to fifth annual rain

Sample	DO (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)
Al-s 1	4.60	1.40	3.26	0.02	0.06	2.124	0.901
Al-s 2	4.80	1.20	2.86	ND	0.05	1.180	0.501
Al-s 3	5.10	1.30	3.10	ND	0.04	0.960	0.391
Al-s 4	5.30	1.20	2.86	ND	0.03	0.732	0.286
Al-s 5	5.10	1.40	3.41	ND	0.02	0.659	0.257
Zn-s 1	5.10	1.60	3.72	0.03	0.09	1.040	0.586
Zn-s 2	5.40	1.40	3.33	ND	0.04	0.624	0.352
Zn-s 3	5.50	1.20	2.86	ND	0.03	0.424	0.230
Zn-s 4	5.80	1.20	2.86	ND	0.02	0.416	0.234
Zn-s 5	5.60	1.30	3.13	ND	ND	0.395	0.223
WHO	4.00	5	10	50	250	75	50

Al-s: aluminium-roofing sheet, Zn-s: zinc roofing sheet, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5: first, second, third, fourth and fifth rain fall.

Table 2: Chemical test result from Asbestos and thatch Roofs from first to fifth annual rain

Sample	DO (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)
Asb 1	5.40	1.80	4.19	0.19	0.51	2.816	6.095
Asb 2	5.70	1.50	3.57	0.07	0.34	1.584	3.428
Asb 3	5.90	1.50	3.57	0.04	0.27	1.248	2.412
Asb 4	6.10	1.30	3.10	0.03	0.21	1.012	2.068
Asb 5	5.80	1.40	3.20	0.01	0.17	1.006	0.879
Tha 1	5.60	2.10	4.88	0.06	0.21	3.536	1.993
Tha 2	5.80	1.70	4.05	ND	0.13	2.288	1.289
Tha 3	5.70	1.40	3.33	ND	0.11	1.696	0.198
Tha 4	5.80	1.20	2.86	ND	0.08	1.428	0.838
Tha 5	5.70	1.50	3.66	ND	0.05	1.224	0.718
WHO	4.00	5	10	50	250	75	50

Asb: asbestos roof, Tha: thatch roof, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5: first, second, third, fourth and fifth rain fall.

Table 3: Microbial test result from Aluminium and zinc Roofs from first to fifth annual rain

Sample	T.Coliform (MPN/100mL)	F.Coliform (MPN/100mL)	E.Coli (MPN/100mL)	THB (cfu/L)	THF (cfu/L)
Al-s 1	70.00	ND	ND	1.97	0.90
Al-s 2	40.00	ND	ND	1.38	0.34
Al-s 3	20.00	ND	ND	1.15	0.28
Al-s 4	20.00	ND	ND	1.07	0.19
Al-s 5	20.00	ND	ND	0.98	0.08
Zn-s 1	90.00	ND	ND	2.23	1.04
Zn-s 2	40.00	ND	ND	1.72	0.63
Zn-s 3	40.00	ND	ND	1.48	0.57
Zn-s 4	20.00	ND	ND	1.27	0.30
Zn-s 5	20.00	ND	ND	1.19	0.20
WHO	0	0	0	0	0

Al-s: aluminium-roofing sheet, Zn-s: zinc roofing sheet, THB: total heterotrophic bacterial, THF: total heterotrophic fungi. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5: first, second, third, fourth and fifth rain fall.

Table 4: Microbial test result from Asbestos and thatch Roofs from first to fifth annual rain

Sample	T.Coliform (MPN/100mL)	F.Coliform (MPN/100mL)	E.Coli (MPN/100mL)	THB (cfu/L)	THF (cfu/L)
Asb 1	140.00	20.00	ND	2.51	1.32
Asb 2	90.00	ND	ND	1.97	0.87
Asb 3	70.00	ND	ND	1.74	0.79
Asb 4	60.00	ND	ND	1.49	0.48
Asb 5	40.00	ND	ND	1.27	0.34
Tha 1	110.00	ND	ND	2.44	1.23
Tha 2	60.00	ND	ND	1.78	0.79
Tha 3	40.00	ND	ND	1.52	0.61
Tha 4	40.00	ND	ND	1.43	0.36
Tha 5	20.00	ND	ND	1.31	0.28
WHO	0	0	0	0	0

Asb: asbestos roof, Tha: thatch roof, THB: total heterotrophic bacteria, THF: total heterotrophic fungi. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5: first, second, third, fourth and fifth rain fall.

The chemical and microbiological properties of harvested rainwater samples for the months of February to August 2019 are presented in Tables 1-4. Values obtained in this study were compared with the World Health Organization standard (WHO) for drinkable water quality.

Biochemical Analysis Discussion

The biochemical concentrations in the harvested rainwater sample were considerably good. The Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) were consistently moderate (Table1) and (Table2) in all the samples from the area. Although the Chemical Oxygen Demand values were generally higher in all the samples than Biochemical Oxygen Demand, due to the presence of organic compounds and certain inorganic ions such as Fe^{2+} , which are not biochemically oxidizable. The BOD values ranged from 1.40–1.40 mg/L and 1.60–1.30 mg/L, for aluminum and zinc roofing sheets samples respectively from first to fifth rainfall (Table 1), and 1.80–1.40 mg/L and 2.10–1.50 mg/L for asbestos, and thatch roofs samples from first to fifth rainfall (Table 2).

The COD values ranged from 3.26–3.41 mg/L, 3.72–3.13 mg/L, 4.19–3.20 mg/L and 4.88–3.66 mg/L for aluminum, zinc, asbestos, and thatch roofs samples, respectively, from the first to fifth flush (in table 1&2). The BOD and COD tend to reduce as the months and number of flush increase. All the values of COD and BOD recorded fell below WHO recommended standard of 10 mg/L and 5mg/L.

Dissolved oxygen values tend to increase from the first flush to the fifth flush in Tables 1 and 2 in all the roofing materials. The DO values are slightly higher than that WHO recommended standard of 4.0 mg/L. According to the WHO (2010), no health-based guideline value is recommended.

Elemental Analysis Discussion

The elemental results in (Table1&2) show calcium and magnesium concentration of the different roofing materials during the various rainfall periods in the study area. The calcium values ranged from 1.040 – 0.395 mg/L, 2.124 – 0.659 mg/L, 2.816–1.006 mg/L, and 3.536–1.224 mg/L for zinc, aluminum, asbestos and thatch roofs, respectively from the first fifth flush.

It was observed from the same (Table1&2) that water samples collected from asbestos roofing sheet gave the highest magnesium concentrations, 6.095 mg/L in all four roofing sheets. This could be traceable to the level of magnesium and calcium carbonate content that can be leached from the roofing material. Higher values of calcium were observed in thatch roofs as well. Calcium and Magnesium in water gives rise to hardness of water. There is a noticeable decrease in the values of calcium and magnesium with increase in the number of rainfall. They all fell below the recommended maximum standard value of 75 mg/L and 50mg/L of WHO for calcium and magnesium respectively.

Anions Results Discussion

The anions concentrations in the harvested rainwater sample were consistently low (Table1 & 2). Nitrate values obtained from all the water samples analyzed (Table1&2) fell below the WHO standard of 50 mg/L. There was no trace of nitrate in all the roofing materials after second flush except for only asbestos roof. Sulphate values obtained from all the water samples analyzed were consistently low (Table1& 2) in all the samples from the area. The presence of this little amount of sulphates on the roofing sheets may be due to evaporating oceans and seas sprays that leave tiny particles of sulphate salts such as Sodium Sulphate in the air that are later deposited on the rooftops and some human and industrial activities. It was observed that the

sulphate content decreases with respect to increase in number of rainfall. The WHO limit for sulphate is 250mg/L.

Microbiology Results Discussion

Total Coliform, Total Heterotrophic Fungi (THF) and Total Heterotrophic Bacterial (THB) (table 3&4) are in all the roofing materials from the first to the fifth flush, which may be due to small animal i.e. rats, lizards, bats etc and birds' feces deposited on top of the roofing sheets. There is no trace of *E.coli* in the four roofing materials (Table 3&4), there is also a total flush out of all the fecal coliform from all the rooftops after the first flush in all the rooftops, but there are still total coliform, THB and THF after the fifth flush. There is a great noticeable decrease in the microbial pollution from all the rooftops, from the first flush to the fifth flush.

Conclusion

This study in Warri shows that the quality of harvested rainwater depends on both the type of roof and the environmental conditions, which include not only the local climate but also atmospheric pollution. The presence of THB, THF, total coliform bacteria, fecal coliform, and *E. coli* in the harvested rainwater indicates that the water is contaminated and may pose a health hazard. All rainwater samples from the fifth flush and above are safe for domestic uses such as washing, mopping, laundry, bathing, toilet flushing, and other cleaning tasks after being subjected to simple water treatment like boiling. Rainwater harvested from asbestos and thatch roofing materials contains a high amount of pollutants and is therefore not safe for consumption, except for domestic uses like washing, mopping, cleaning, laundry, bathing, and toilet flushing.

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